

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINANTS OF ETHNIC BELONGING IN ADOLESCENTS. CROSS-CULTURAL INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

The sense of belonging is the expression of a fundamental need of each individual. It allows a person to feel fully a member of the community and it expresses the need for recognition and to have a role with associated expectations. In this sense, conformity with the perceptions, values, principles, patterns of behavior, norms and obligations arising from the institutions of a community, as well as respect for certain traditions, customs and concrete relational arrangements, is an essential condition for the recognition of belonging. Thus, the goal of this research work is to highlight the loyalty of young generations, Moldovan adolescents, to their community, which is translated into the sense of belonging. Particularly, we refer, here, to that attitude with which trust and unconditional attachment to the community and its institutions are expressed, whether this trust and attachment are supported and motivated by a conscious experience of reality, or whether they are based only on a representation of it, or on an idealization resulting from ideological conditioning.

Keywords: sense of belonging, identity, identification process, immigrant adolescents, ethnic identification, loyalty.

Introduction

The term *belonging* is used to denote an individual's affiliation with a community that can be defined by social, cultural, legal or territorial criteria. It can be a group, an association, a community, a socio-professional category or a social class. In this first sense, the term *belonging* indicates a condition for the inclusion of an individual in a community or his/her recognition as a member of it (Hobsbawn, 1983). Thus, the issues related to this use of the term refer to the modalities of inclusion (or exclusion) and the presuppositions of recognition (non-recognition or disavowal) on which both the constitution and the composition depend, as well as the social limits of the community taken into account and the relations between its members.

The second meaning of the term *belonging*, closely linked to the first one, is used to describe the feeling of identity, which is the expression of an adherence, of a cultural, ideological or emotional nature, to the distinctive and founding contents of a community. When speaking about belonging in this context, we refer to the process of identifying people with the community they belong to. Therefore, this identification implies a self-recognition in the prevailing and characteristic values, norms, lifestyles and behaviors of a community or sharing its history and traditions, as long as these distinctive features or historical-cultural matrix are socially recognized (Wallerstein, 1991).

In the same line, the concept of belonging is attributed to specific ways of social relations between individuals. We are talking about *belonging relationships*, alluding to various forms of exchange, cooperation or protection, which are established between individuals, when they assign each other a connection, a common goal or interest, the same faith, a common family, a social and cultural origin. Problems related to this meaning of the term relate in particular to the processes of setting up and reproducing social groups or

networks, in which similar privileged relationships are created and the recognition of individuals as components of these groups, where the rules of access (or exclusion) depend on one's position or role, the advantages, but also the constraints of being part of it.

Similarly, the term *belonging* is used to describe a fundamental human psychological need, which manifests itself since childhood and whose satisfaction depends on emotional balance, self-esteem and motivational processes, sense of acceptance, self-acceptance, sense of security and self-perception. In this sense, the term refers both to the dimension that has to do with the need to care for the other and to entrust oneself to the care of another. In other words, we refer to a need which is expressed in those emotional connections of understanding and intimacy which characterize interpersonal relationships and which acquire special importance in the construction and reproduction of the identity (Blau, Schwartz, 1985).

Therefore, the meanings of the notion obviously refer to different dimensions of belonging, thematized in the social sciences, appealing to specific aspects and referring to the conditions of recognition of individuals as members of a social group or category.

In this context, as a constitutive element, we can highlight first of all the family bond (Hobsbawn, 1983). Although the foundations of belonging are diversified and multiplied as well as the dimensions and spaces of identity expression, the family bond continues to take the form of the primary foundation of the sense of belonging, which is established in interpersonal relationships and which is projected onto forms of organization of social life. Thus, the character attributed to family belonging acts on the process of establishing the same social identity of individuals. The strength and persistence of this connection can be traced to the social importance attributed to the relations of consanguinity and affinity, as discriminatory criteria: both for establishing

emotional relationships and mutual care, which are functional to physical reproduction and satisfaction of the basic psychological needs of each individual in the different phases of his life, as well as to the cooperative relations, characterized by a high degree of trust and loyalty. Cooperative relationships, which can be activated according to different needs and purposes, are related to everyday life as well as to social relations, economic and political activity, which take place within any community.

A second basis of belonging can be identified in the socio-cultural matrix of a community, or rather in that set of distinctive elements such as history, traditions, language, religion, customs and lifestyles, social and economic patterns and organization (Held, 1989, p. 192). In other words, we refer to those elements on which the collective identity of a people, a community or even a generation is built. The recognition of a common socio-cultural matrix, which can also be summarized in a pre-eminent or distinctive factor (of a religious, ideological, historical and ethno-linguistic nature), is the foundation of that type of belonging, which is expressed in the form of a sense of collective identity and which is symbolically evoked by socially codified cultural images or patterns that are sufficiently shared both within and outside the community in question. This feeling manifests itself in the social representations which are nurtured by historical memory, cultural production, institutions and the normative and value frameworks of a people or a community, as well as in all those events and symbolic modalities that perform a supporting function for the complex process of contemporary identity maintenance and redefinition.

Sharing the same social status can also act as a basis for bonds and feelings of belonging, namely the recognition of a common condition, which derives from the social role which is covered and the position in the social stratification with all which follows from it. Thus, the more social importance is given to the status, the more effective it is in determining a sense of identity and belonging (Held, 1989, p. 201). This meaning can also have a negative connotation and therefore be at the origin of forms of prejudice, exclusion or social marginalization.

Another foundation of belonging can be identified in sharing common goals (Mouffe, 1992). This refers to belonging to a group, to an association, which pursues objectives that can be of an economic, political, religious, cultural, ideological or territorial control nature. These goals can be embedded in the cultural and regulatory framework of a society, where the organizations pursuing them enjoy social legitimacy. In some cases, they may also be an expression of some forms of social deviance, as organizations which operate more or less covertly, according to illegal methods, subversives of the institutions of a society, or whose actions cause widespread social disapproval, even if they do not explicitly conflict with any rule sanctioned by the regulations in force.

Finally, belonging can be based on common experience, shared experiences and life situations, whether they are current or from the past (Featherstone, 1991). Particularly, we refer to the founding elements of that

type of belonging, which are expressed in the field of interpersonal relationships, from those established within the so-called primary groups to those which are built in spaces and opportunities of everyday life. The most diverse feelings of belonging range from those that arise from privileged interpersonal relationships, to those that unite people of the same generation who feel that they have shared life conditions, ideals or crucial historical events. Those feelings which connect fellow soldiers with a dramatic war experience on the same front, as well as those that establish among members of a small community, are included, too. The more significant life experiences are in an individual's biography, the stronger their sense of belonging is. This is established with those who have shared or share such experiences and with those who are perceived as a significant presence in one's existence and memory (Robertson, 1992).

Referring to Moldovan adolescents in the diaspora, loyalty to their belonging can be the disposition to assume the position of protection and defense of the image and good name of the community to which they belong, or that mental attitude, often unconscious, but sometimes instrumental, for which they are inclined to justify and legitimize their actions. It can be an internalized identity content as a result of a „natural” identification with the community of belonging induced by socialization processes or by the fact that one has an already sedimented experience of this belonging from childhood, or it can be an identity content that emerges and manifests itself at a certain moment of the individual biographical path, as a result of choices which were made, activities which were undertaken, intellectual development, relationships which begun (or were broken), vicissitudes in the personal sphere or events occurring in the social and environmental context in which people are currently embedded. This content can be added to pre-existing content, creating a new identity structure and with it a new sense of belonging to (or redefinition of) a community, or it can manifest itself as a substitute effect of other identity content, which for some reason lost its meaning.

The purpose of this work is therefore to capture the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity in order to see the importance of ethnic belonging and to assess the interrelations between majority and minority ethnic groups as parameters of ethnic identity in the case of Moldovan adolescents who are immigrants in Italy and Moldovan adolescents who live in the Republic of Moldova.

Research hypothesis: The parameters of ethnic identification in Moldovan adolescents are determined by status and place of living.

Methodology and methods

In order to study the determinants of ethnic belonging, both in the case of Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy and Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova, we used O. L. Romanova questionnaire, which is designed to measure the parameters of ethnic identification: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity* (questions: -5, -7, +8, +9, -11, -13, +21), *the importance of ethnic identity* (questions: +1, +3, +4, +6,

+10, +12, -14) and the assessment of interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups (questions: +2, +15, +16, -17, +18, -19, +20). The questionnaire is made up of 21 statements, which reflect different points of view. As for the answers, they contain a degree of agreement or disagreement according to the following scale: 1 - *absolutely agree*; 2 - *agree rather than disagree*; 0 - *cannot answer*; -1 - *rather disagree than agree*; -2 - *absolutely disagree*. Direct and indirect questions are taken into account in the evaluation.

Thus, the importance of the evaluation should be changed to a reflective one in the case of questions marked with a "minus" sign. For instance, the answer: *absolutely agree* will be given 5 points, but by changing the importance to a reflective one, the respondent will be given 1 point, the answer: *agree rather than disagree* will be given 4 points (reflective - 2 points), the answer: *cannot answer* - 3 points, the answer: *rather disagree than agree* - 2 points (reflective - 4 points) and the answer: *absolutely disagree* - 1 point (reflective - 5 points). As a result, the mean values (M) were calculated for each scale and group of respondents, and the

extent to which the presented parameters characterize the evaluation of Moldovan adolescents was determined, as well as the standard deviation (Стефаненко, 1999, p. 48).

Subsequently, the empirical data comparison procedure was carried out with regard to the parameters of ethnic identification among Moldovan adolescents in Italy and Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova, using the T-Test for independent samples.

The investigation took place between December 2018 and October 2019, the research sample being made up of 215 teenagers (110 from the Republic of Moldova, Chisinau and Florești and 105 from Italy, regions: Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria and Veneto), aged between 14 and 18.

Results and discussions

In order to reveal statistically significant differences between Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy, we used the independent samples T-Test.

The following data was highlighted after the results were obtained:

Table 1.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy

	The mean of Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of Moldovan adolescents in Italy +/- The Standard deviation	T-Test	Significance of the difference between the means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	25,40 +/- 4,86	17,90 +/- 6,85	9,210	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The importance of ethnic belonging	25,59 +/- 4,75	18,15 +/- 6,93	9,139	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	27,25 +/- 5,76	16,01 +/- 7,51	12,282	p < 0,001	p < 0,001

We observed statistically significant differences for all scales as a result of comparing data on the parameters of expressing a sense of ethnic identification: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity* (T=9,210, p<0,001), *the importance of ethnic belonging* (T=9,139, p<0,001), *the interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups* (T=12,282, p<0,001). In all cases, Moldovan adolescents from the Republic of Moldova obtained significantly higher results compared to Moldovan immigrant adolescents from Italy, which in our opinion can be explained by the awareness of being part of a stable community, which is an important reference in the ethnic identification pathway and it has an influence on their perception associated with culture, ethnicity, religion, customs and traditions, which leads directly to the establishment of a deep sense of national pride and a sense of inclusion and perception of their own personal values in the context of their daily lives, feeling themselves as full members of the Moldovan community.

However, when we refer to the results of Moldovan adolescents in Italy, regarding the ethnic identification parameters, we can observe *the fingerprint* of the context in which they currently live, the minority position they hold in their host country, along with the idea of being suspended between two worlds, which feeds their state of non-acceptance and „inadequacy” to both contexts, since „there has not been that integral and total adherence to their own world, culture, society”, which would develop their sentimental, psychological bond with the Republic of Moldova, an identity value which is an exclusive reference for a people.

Furthermore, in order to obtain a more complex picture regarding the ethnic identification parameters, we made several comparisons between Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy, according to gender and place of living. The results are reflected in the following tables:

Table 2.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy, according to gender

	The mean of male adolescents +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of female adolescents +/- The Standard deviation	T-Test	Significance of the difference between means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	21,27 +/- 6,42	22,19 +/- 7,51	-0,968	p = 0,334	
The importance of ethnic belonging	21,24 +/- 6,71	22,65 +/- 7,20	-1,482	p = 0,140	
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	20,78 +/- 8,71	22,70 +/- 8,67	-1,619	p = 0,107	

The received results did not reveal any statistically significant differences.

Table 3.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between male adolescents in Italy and female adolescents in Italy, according to gender and place of living

	The mean of male adolescents in Italy +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of female adolescents in Italy +/- The Standard deviation	T-Test	Significance of the difference between means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	18,66 +/- 6,15	16,81 +/- 7,70	1,310	p = 0,194	
The importance of ethnic belonging	18,71 +/- 6,47	17,35 +/- 7,54	0,963	p = 0,339	
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	16,85 +/- 8,00	14,79 +/- 6,63	1,440	p = 0,153	

Once the results have been processed, in terms of expressing a sense of ethnic identification, among male adolescents and female adolescents in Italy, no statistically significant differences were found in any of the given scales: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity*

($T = 1,310$, $p = 0,194$), *the importance of ethnic belonging* ($T = 0,963$, $p = 0,339$), *the interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups* ($T = 1,440$, $p = 0,153$).

Table 3.1.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova, according to gender and place of living

	The mean of male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova +/- The Standard deviation	T-Test	Significance of the difference between means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	25,02 +/- 4,76	25,64 +/- 4,94	-0,649	p = 0,517	
The importance of ethnic belonging	24,88 +/- 5,24	26,04 +/- 4,40	-1,253	p = 0,213	
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	26,44 +/- 6,25	27,78 +/- 5,40	-1,188	p = 0,237	

Similarly, as in the case of adolescents in Italy, we observe that there are no significant differences between male adolescents and female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova in any of the given scales: *the*

sense of belonging to an ethnic identity ($T = -0,649$, $p = 0,517$), *the importance of ethnic belonging* ($T = -1,253$, $p = 0,213$), *the interrelations between majority and minority ethnic groups* ($T = -1,188$, $p = 0,237$).

Table 3.1.2.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between female adolescents in Italy and female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova, according to gender and place of living

	The mean of female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of female adolescents in Italy +/- The Standard deviation	T- Test	Significance of the difference between means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	25,64 +/- 4,94	16,81 +/- 7,70	6,685	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The importance of ethnic belonging	26,04 +/- 4,40	17,35 +/- 7,54	6,850	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	27,78 +/- 5,40	14,79 +/- 6,63	11,241	p < 0,001	p < 0,001

Comparing the obtained results regarding the parameters of expression of the sense of ethnic identification, we can find significant differences between the two groups of subjects on all scales: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity* (T=6,685, p<0,001), *the importance of ethnic belonging* (T=6,850, p<0,001),

the interrelations between majority and minority ethnic groups (T=11,241, p<0,001). In this sense, female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova obtained statistically significantly higher results than Moldovan female adolescents in Italy in all cases.

Table 3.1.3.

Comparison of ethnic identification parameters between male adolescents in Italy and male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova, according to gender and place of living

	The mean of male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova +/- The Standard deviation	The mean of male adolescents in Italy +/- The Standard deviation	T- Test	Significance of the difference between means (p)	The significance level
The sense of belonging to an ethnic identity	25,02 +/- 4,76	18,66 +/- 6,15	5,964	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The importance of ethnic belonging	24,88 +/- 5,24	18,71 +/- 6,47	5,186	p < 0,001	p < 0,001
The interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups	26,44 +/- 6,25	16,85 +/- 8,00	6,881	p < 0,001	p < 0,001

After analyzing the received results, as in the case of female adolescents, we can see significant differences between the two groups of subjects on all scales: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity* (T=5,964, p<0,001), *the importance of ethnic belonging* (T=5,186, p<0,001), *the interrelations between majority and minority ethnic groups* (T=6,881, p<0,001). At the same time, male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova obtained statistically significantly higher results than Moldovan male adolescents in Italy in all cases.

Conclusions

1. Based on the results mentioned above, we can clearly notice that the importance of the parameters concerning the expression of the sense of ethnic identification was different among the adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy. Therefore, compared to Moldovan adolescents in Italy, adolescents in the Republic of Moldova obtained statistically significant higher scores on all scales: *the sense of belonging to an ethnic identity*, *the importance of*

ethnic belonging, *the interrelations between the majority and minority ethnic groups*.

2. The results of comparisons between adolescents from the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents from Italy with regard to the ethnic identification parameters highlighted the following:

- In terms of gender (in the case of adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and adolescents in Italy), no statistically significant differences were found.

- In terms of gender and place of living, we remark that female adolescents in the Republic of Moldova show statistically significant results on all parameters of ethnic identification compared to Moldovan adolescents in Italy.

The same situation was revealed in the case of male adolescents, where male adolescents in the Republic of Moldova obtained statistically significant results at all scales, with respect to Moldovan adolescents in Italy.

Thus, in the light of the interpreted data, we can conclude that Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova manifest an ingrained sense of belonging,

fuelled by a lot of emotional involvement, recognized as an essential reference of their identity: „*Moldova and I are like mother and son. I feel part of it, because I was born from the dust of this land*” (A., 18 years old).

However, regarding Moldovan adolescents who are immigrants in Italy, we can observe that the importance of the sense of belonging bifurcates into double belonging, since over time adolescents establish close ties with both the country of origin and the host country. And it is not excluded that the relationship with the current place of living, in time, becomes much more significant in relation to the place of origin. In this sense, one adolescent affirms that Italy, for him, is like „*a nest and he is like a cuckoo*”, attributing a lot of importance to his origin. Of course, this requires further research to clarify the genesis of this feeling, which certainly influences their perception of belonging on the background of migration.

References

1. Blau, P., Schwartz, J. *Crosscutting Social/ Circles. Testing a Macrostructural Theory of Intergroup Relations*, New York: Academic Press, 1985.
2. Featherstone, M. *Global Culture. Nationalism, Globalization and Modernity*, London: Sage, 1991.
3. Held, D. *Citizenship and Autonomy*. In: *Political/ Theory and the Modern State*, Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1989, pp. 189-213.
4. Hobsbawn, E., Ranger, T. *The Invention of Tradition*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983.
5. Mouffe, C. *Dimensions of Radical Democracy. Pluralism, Citizenship, Community*, London: Verso, 1992.
6. Robertson, R. *Globalization. Social/ Theory and Global Culture*, London: Sage, 1992.
7. Wallerstein, I. *Unthinking Social/ Sciences: The Limits of Nineteenth-Century Paradigms*, Cambridge: Polity Press, 1991.
8. Стефаненко Т. Г. Социальная психология этнической идентичности. Диссертация на соискание учёной степени доктора психологических наук, Москва: Московский Государственный Университет имени М. В. Ломоносова, 1999, 48 с.